

Phosphine-free synthesis of p-type copper (I) selenide nanocrystals in hot coordinating solvents

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Supporting information

1. Chemicals: Copper chloride (CuCl, 99.999%) and elemental selenium (Se, 99.99%) were purchased from Strem chemicals. Oleylamine (OLAM, 70%), oleic acid (OLAC, 90%) and 1-octadecene (ODE, 90%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Anhydrous ethanol, toluene and chloroform were purchased from Carlo Erba reagents. All chemicals were used as received.

2. Synthesis of nanocrystals: Anhydrous CuCl (0.099 g, 1 mmol) was first added to a mixture of 5 ml of oleylamine and 5 ml of 1-octadecene (ODE) in a reaction flask. After pumping to vacuum for 1 h at 80 °C using a standard Schlenk line, the reaction mixture was put under constant nitrogen flow. The temperature was then set at 300, 315 or 330 °C, depending on the synthesis. A Se-ODE solution was freshly prepared in the glove box by mixing 0.039 g of Se (0.5 mmol) with 1 ml of ODE. The solution was heated at 180-200 °C on a hot plate and shaken vigorously for a few seconds using a vortexer, it was then taken out of the glove box and sonicated for 10-15 minutes. Under nitrogen flow, the solution was transferred into a syringe equipped with a large needle (12 gauge external diameter) and it was injected quickly into the flask. After injection, the temperature of the reaction mixture dropped to ~280 °C, and it was allowed to recover to the pre-injection value. The overall reaction time after injection was 15 min, after which the flask was rapidly cooled to room temperature. Once at room temperature, 5 ml of toluene was added to the reaction mixture, and the resulting solution was transferred into a vial under nitrogen flow, and the vial was then stored inside a glove box.

A test synthesis was also carried out by heating the CuCl/oleylamine/octadecene mixture at 320 °C for 8 minutes, but without injecting the Se:ODE solution. The product obtained in this case was elemental Cu, as revealed by X-ray diffraction (See Figure S6).

3. Size selection: The mother solution containing the as-synthesized nanocrystals was often contaminated with large, platelet-shaped nanocrystals. These big crystals could be precipitated selectively by careful centrifugation (all these procedures were carried out in the glove box): a few

drops of absolute ethanol were added to the mother solution, after which the solution was centrifuged at 500 rpm for 1 minute. The precipitate formed at the bottom contained mainly the large platelets. The procedure could be repeated one more time to ensure quantitative precipitation of the large platelets. The supernatant contained much smaller nanocrystals, which could be precipitated by addition of a few ml of ethanol, followed by centrifugation at 2000 rpm for several minutes.

4. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Low-resolution TEM images were recorded on a JEOL JEM 1011 microscope operating at 100 kV. High resolution TEM (HRTEM) measurements and energy filtered images were performed with a JEOL JEM-2200FS microscope, equipped with a field emission gun working at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV, a CEOS spherical aberration corrector and an Omega filter. Energy filtered images were acquired using a contrast aperture of about 10mrad to reduce aberrations (mostly chromatic). An elastic image (or zero/loss image) was acquired as a reference area with a 10eV energy slit. Chemical maps from Cu L (931eV) and Se L (1436eV) edges were obtained by acquiring three images (one post-edge and two pre-edge) respectively, to extract the background, with an energy slit of 50eV for Cu and 60eV for Se. The samples for TEM analysis were prepared in a glove box by depositing a few drops of a dilute solution of nanocrystals onto carbon-coated Cu grids. The latter were then transferred immediately into the microscope.

5. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). High resolution SEM images were recorded on a Raith150-TWO Electron Beam Lithography (EBL) system equipped with a thermal-field-emission source and a Gemini column.

6. Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). XRD measurements were performed with a Rigaku SmartLab X-ray diffractometer. Concentrated nanocrystal solutions were spread on top of a silicon miscut substrate, after which the sample was allowed to dry and was then measured in parallel beam reflection geometry $\theta/2\theta$.

7. UV-Vis-NIR Absorption Spectroscopy. Optical absorption measurements were carried out using a Varian Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. Nanocrystals were dispersed in trichloroethylene for this purpose.

8. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. XPS measurements were carried out on a Thermo Scientific Escalab 250Xi spectrometer. A thick film of nanocrystals was prepared on a Si-substrate by drop-casting.

9. Thermoelectric measurement: An Agilent 34410A 6 1/2 digital multimeter (DM) and a Suss Microtech PM5 probe station were used for the measurements. The lower measurement limit of DC voltage was 1 μ V. The probe station was equipped with tungsten probes. One of the probes was cooled by immersion into liquid nitrogen immediately before the measurement and was then allowed to warm up under ambient conditions. A thin film of Cu_{2-x}Se nanocrystals was prepared on a glass slide by drop-casting.

Figure S1. STEM-EDS acquisition and HRTEM measurements on a big hexagonal platelet separated for the mother solution by size selection precipitation. (a) HAADF (high angle annular dark filed) STEM image; (b) EDS spectrum from the area indicated in (a), with a resulting Cu:Se ratio for the hexagonal platelet of 1.2:1. This ratio differs from the 1:1 expected ratio, most likely due to the concomitant presence of Cu_{2-x}Se nanocrystals on both sides of the platelet.

Figure S2. HAADF-STEM image from a group of nanocrystals (left panel) with the corresponding integrated EDS spectra (right panel) from the area delimited by the red line. The Cu:Se ratio is found to be 1.86:1.

Figure S3. HRTEM images from nanocrystals of different Cu-Se phases. (a) Detail of two $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{Se}$ nanocrystals with fcc structure showing (111) lattice planes (interplanar distance 3.32 Å); (b) a rare CuSe nanocrystal with hcp structure observed along the [001] zone axis and showing (110) lattice planes (interplanar distance 1.96 Å).

Figure S4. Fitted XRD patterns of two batches of copper (I) selenide samples synthesized at 300 °C. The XRD patterns were analyzed by using a whole profile fitting Rietveld-based program, named FullProf.¹ The crystal structure model used in the fits was α -Cu_{1.8}Se (JCPDS card 71-0044)² having Fm-3m space group and a=b=c=5.787 Å cell size. Refined parameters were the unit cell size and the peak full width at half maximum.

Figure S5. XRD patterns of nanocrystals synthesized at (a) 315 °C and at (b) 330 °C. A qualitative analysis of the crystalline phase content was performed on both samples using the QUALX program.³ The XRD patterns show presence of metallic copper (ICDD-PDF2 card 00-004-0836) as well tetragonal Bellidoite Cu₂Se phase (ICDD-PDF2 card 00-029-0575).

Figure S6. XRD pattern of the product recovered after heating the CuCl/oleylamine/octadecene mixture at 320 °C for 8 minutes, but without injecting the Se:ODE solution. The product obtained in this case was elemental Cu.

Figure S7 Sample 1 (in black) and Sample 2 (in red) were Cu_{2-x}Se films on glass protected by PMMA coverage from oxidation. Sample 2 was treated in hydrazine. Sample 3 (in green) and Sample 4 (in blue) were Cu_{2-x}Se films on glass without protection and hence slightly oxidized. Sample 4 was treated in hydrazine. Hydrazine treatment is known to reduce the inter-particle spacing within the film⁴ and we find consistently that the peak resulting from the direct band gap transition is slightly red-shifted after hydrazine treatment. The spectra of the oxidized samples show significantly broader peak structures, which could be due to various factors (broadening of size distributions and/or modified absorption arising from the new oxidized species for example).

References

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4. Talapin, D. V.; Murray, C. B., *Science* **2005**, 310, 5745, 86-89.